

International Journal on Natural Language Computing (IJNLC)

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SCOPE OF THE JOURNAL

Natural Language Processing is a programmed approach to analyze text that is based on both a set of theories and a set of technologies. This forum aims to bring together researchers who have designed and build software that will analyze, understand, and generate languages that humans use naturally to address computers.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Phonology, Morphology
- Chunking/Shallow Parsing
- Parsing/Grammatical Formalisms
- Semantic Processing
- Lexical Semantics
- Ontology
- Linguistic Resources
- Statistical and Knowledge based methods
- POS tagging
- Discourse
- Paraphrasing/Entailment/Generation
- Machine Translation
- Information Retrieval
- Text Mining
- Information Extraction
- Question Answering
- Dialog Systems
- Spoken Language Processing
- Speech Recognition and Synthesis

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All manuscripts will be subject to a well established, fair, unbiased peer review and refereeing procedure, and are considered on the basis of their significance, novelty and usefulness to the Journals readership. The reviewing structure will always ensure the anonymity of the referees & it will be reviewed by 3 experts in the field. The review output will be one of the following decisions:

1. Accept
2. Accept with minor changes
3. Weak Accept with major changes
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